

NATIONAL BUREAU OF STATISTICS

Nigerian Domestic and Foreign Debt

(Q2 2019)

Report Date: October 2019

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Executive Summary

Nigerian States and Federal Debt Stock data as at 30th June 2019 reflected that the country's total public debt portfolio stood at N25.70trn.

Further disaggregation of Nigeria's total public debt showed that N8.32trn or 32.38% of the debt was external while N17.38trn or 67.62% of the debt was domestic.

Similarly, total domestic debt was N3.97 trillion with Lagos state accounting for 12.08% of the total domestic debt stock while Yobe State has the least debt stock in this category with a contribution of 0.68% to the total domestic debt stock.

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

ABIA STATE

Land Area: 2,440 sq mi

Population: 3,616,382

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N25,609,616,667.34

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N7,912,596,332.05

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$98,028,293.33

31st Dec 2018

30th June 2018

Total (\$)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

\$98,582,798.91

\$100,217,589.59

\$98,028,293.33

-2.18

-0.56

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N68,003,077,437.81

N67,017,185,656.92

N57,467,618,625.51

18.33

1.47

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

ADAMAWA STATE

Land Area: 14, 254 sq mi

Population: 4,111,706

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N23,261,208,811.40

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N5,014,807,850.67

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$94,113,674.40

\$6,500,000.00

31st Dec 2018

\$97,790,423.73

30th June 2018

\$57,860,541.54

Total (\$)

\$100,613,674.40

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

73.89

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

2.89

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N95,219,782,086.14

N89,659,119,455.46

N67,460,656,267.08

41.15

6.20

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

AKWA IBOM STATE

Land Area: 2,734 sq mi

Population: 5,272,029

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N86,309,360,838.49

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N20,464,607,233.41

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$44,935,625.88

31st Dec 2018

\$45,657,647.14

30th June 2018

\$48,385,866.53

Total (\$)

\$44,935,625.88

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-7.13

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-1.58

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

N206,414,472,059.83

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

N198,663,229,326.07

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

N179,714,994,143.75

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

14.86

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

3.90

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

ANAMBRA STATE

Land Area: 1,870 sq mi

Population: 5,356,592

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N26,163,231,045.41

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N6,073,241,006.13

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$111,783,998.80

31st Dec 2018

\$107,041,487.48

30th June 2018

\$107,438,517.03

Total (\$)

\$111,783,998.80

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

4.04

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

4.43

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

N33,431,158,600.07

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

N33,490,668,536.72

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

N2,612,431,503.89

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

1179.70

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-0.18

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

BAUCHI STATE

Land Area: 18, 965 sq mi

Population: 6,286,719

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N25,508,713,547.52

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N8,268,708,138.19

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$133,705,364.22

31st Dec 2018

\$133,930,757.08

30th June 2018

\$134,907,612.92

Total (\$)

\$133,705,364.22

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-0.89

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-0.17

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N97,502,601,723.17

N92,367,170,606.61

N78,076,937,314.82

24.88

5.56

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

BAYELSA STATE

Land Area: 8,150 sq mi

Population: 2,204,648

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N65,754,784,594.56

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N5,875,518,818.67

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$56,154,690.84

31st Dec 2018

\$56,623,178.71

30th June 2018

\$57,256,211.04

Total (\$)

\$56,154,690.84

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-1.92

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-0.83

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

8.38

2.53

N133,339,375,587.91

N130,043,473,800.97

N123,031,521,306.14

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

BENUE STATE

Land Area: 13,150 sq m

Population: 5,553,037

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N26,042,594,670.85

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N12,131,771,966.24

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$33,936,861.92

31st Dec 2018

\$39,610,851.64

30th June 2018

\$34,750,363.40

Total (\$)

\$33,936,861.92

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-2.34

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-14.32

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N96,905,502,591.02

N97,347,605,190.14

N92,930,649,665.69

4.28

-0.45

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

BORNO STATE

Land Area: 22, 316 sq mi

Population: 5,635,544

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N29,713,746,866.87

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N3,917,848,074.57

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$21,313,198.49

31st Dec 2018

30th June 2018

Total (\$)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

\$21,618,240.11

\$22,292,486.47

\$21,313,198.49

-4.39

-1.41

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N86,861,555,192.24

N68,381,705,608.58

N77,523,662,982.23

12.05

27.02

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

CROSS RIVER STATE

Land Area: 7,782 sq mi

Population: 3,741,838

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N17,236,760,150.47

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N16,731,425,493.77

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$148,830,721.41

\$43,900,000.00

31st Dec 2018

\$188,773,736.81

30th June 2018

\$193,796,061.81

Total (\$)

\$192,730,721.41

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-0.55

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

2.10

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

N168,819,230,129.37

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

N167,955,848,722.32

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

N124,943,613,082.61

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

35.12

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

0.51

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

DELTA STATE

Land Area: 6,833 sq mi

Population: 5,460,311

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N108,697,421,165.63

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N36,390,689,921.88

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$62,952,056.49

31st Dec 2018

30th June 2018

Total (\$)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

\$63,286,948.43

\$63,825,838.81

\$62,952,056.49

-1.37

-0.53

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N233,564,158,885.47

N228,805,996,159.83

N222,680,606,739.34

4.89

2.08

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EBONYI STATE

Land Area: 2,136 sq mi

Population: 2,791,167

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N21,377,703,339.77

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N5,140,599,994.92

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$76,044,993.97

31st Dec 2018

30th June 2018

Total (\$)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

\$66,653,026.12

\$67,901,721.07

\$76,044,993.97

11.99

14.09

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N42,053,162,874.44

N55,597,352,310.28

N34,515,070,111.77

21.84

-24.36

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EDO STATE

Land Area: 6,873 sq mi

Population: 4,109,499

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N31,864,918,190.52

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N15,441,748,874.50

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$277,735,972.77

31st Dec 2018

\$276,253,922.96

30th June 2018

\$279,029,896.21

Total (\$)

\$277,735,972.77

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-0.46

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

0.54

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N84,002,644,092.96

N86,820,254,212.61

N69,004,633,290.09

21.73

-3.25

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EKITI STATE

Land Area: 2,453 sq mi

Population: 3,157,552

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N19,970,750,042.13

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N5,054,605,377.85

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$) BILATERAL (AFD) (\$) Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$) COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$104,771,792.18

31st Dec 2018
\$106,208,598.19

30th June 2018
\$97,994,770.66

Total (\$)
\$104,771,792.18

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

6.92

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-1.35

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

N86,905,756,443.45

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

N118,011,414,814.34

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

N117,724,274,041.26

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-26.18

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-26.36

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

ENUGU STATE

Land Area: 2,765 sq mi

Population: 4,263,786

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N25,013,513,168.83

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N10,699,049,784.00

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$118,851,839.26

\$6,500,000.00

31st Dec 2018
\$126,177,662.23

30th June 2018
\$127,952,029.92

Total (\$)
\$125,351,839.26

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-2.03

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-0.65

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-1.76

9.30

N60,151,622,506.87

N55,032,067,848.83

N61,231,913,793.95

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

GOMBE STATE

Land Area: 7, 246 sq mi

Population: 3,140,189

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N19,704,992,908.08

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N2,087,431,130.42

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$36,960,036.41

31st Dec 2018

\$37,406,069.57

30th June 2018

\$38,500,292.18

Total (\$)

\$36,960,036.41

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-4.00

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-1.19

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N79,634,209,227.24

N63,337,930,142.60

N41,939,190,055.53

89.88

25.73

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

IMO STATE

Land Area: 2,140 sq mi

Population: 5,214,833

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N26,862,451,370.69

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N10,550,388,151.30

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$61,812,739.83

\$7,000,000.00

31st Dec 2018
\$59,515,586.62

30th June 2018
\$61,277,993.68

Total (\$)
\$68,812,739.83

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

12.30

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

15.62

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

73.94

50.43

N148,598,063,157.77

N98,782,494,271.48

N85,432,191,992.42

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

JIGAWA STATE

Land Area: 8,940 sq mi

Population: 5,640,592

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N28,540,385,721.28

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N5,369,753,095.83

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$31,550,317.67

31st Dec 2018

\$32,008,444.77

30th June 2018

\$32,800,038.17

Total (\$)

\$31,550,317.67

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-3.81

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-1.43

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N38,673,319,242.36

N35,163,169,800.26

N34,488,374,498.85

12.13

9.98

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

KADUNA STATE

Land Area: 17,781 sq mi

Population: 7,976,735

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N32,375,805,354.07

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N22,401,973,458.00

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$223,760,252.12

31st Dec 2018

\$227,252,685.58

30th June 2018

\$232,965,533.73

Total (\$)

\$223,760,252.12

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-3.95

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-1.54

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N97,264,280,664.14

N84,637,112,775.54

N75,606,381,758.43

28.65

14.92

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

KANO STATE

Land Area: 7,773 sq mi

Population: 12,591,871

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N39,976,809,111.31

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N18,564,546,104.36

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$62,219,720.77

31st Dec 2018

30th June 2018

Total (\$)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

\$63,409,069.74

\$65,047,427.46

\$62,219,720.77

-4.35

-1.88

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N117,339,436,693.47

N117,082,317,490.54

N95,420,104,800.47

22.97

0.22

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

KATSINA STATE

Land Area: 9,341 sq mi

Population: 7,569,751

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N30,600,344,094.58

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N4,807,071,081.00

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$61,082,288.27

31st Dec 2018

30th June 2018

Total (\$)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

\$62,133,706.90

\$64,757,964.40

\$61,082,288.27

-5.68

-1.69

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N66,164,163,901.64

N30,852,661,159.10

N30,852,661,159.10

114.45

114.45

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

KEBBI STATE

Land Area: 14,200 sq mi

Population: 4,286,319

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N25,613,287,221.60

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N4,728,501,342.76

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$44,918,042.07

31st Dec 2018

\$45,605,534.73

30th June 2018

\$46,759,780.42

Total (\$)

\$44,918,042.07

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-3.94

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-1.51

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N59,598,378,104.63

N67,442,333,186.56

N53,874,263,625.13

10.62

-11.63

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

KOGI STATE

Land Area: 11,519 sq mi

Population: 4,324,074

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N24,975,272,155.83

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N6,683,808,064.70

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$31,111,476.95

31st Dec 2018

30th June 2018

Total (\$)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

\$31,584,158.36

\$32,371,905.62

\$31,111,476.95

-3.89

-1.50

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N105,135,912,916.85

N84,922,376,449.78

N114,332,341,233.39

-8.04

23.80

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

KWARA STATE

Land Area: 14, 218 sq mi

Population: 3,086,249

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N20,589,752,212.98

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N16,090,373,542.93

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$47,961,939.95

31st Dec 2018

\$48,599,040.43

30th June 2018

\$49,871,457.19

Total (\$)

\$47,961,939.95

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-3.83

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-1.31

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

51.47

3.72

N61,335,531,821.69

N59,135,900,168.96

N40,492,924,816.54

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

LAGOS STATE

Land Area: 1,381 sq mi

Population: 12,100,616

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N58,089,996,966.96

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N205,163,386,767.06

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$1,277,404,576.50

\$143,830,000.00

31st Dec 2018

\$1,426,428,935.47

30th June 2018

\$1,451,639,937.86

Total (\$)

\$1,421,234,576.50

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-2.09

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-0.36

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N479,047,606,006.32

N530,243,773,934.40

N517,367,331,872.95

-7.41

-9.66

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

NASARAWA STATE

Land Area: 10, 470 sq mi

Population: 2,439,113

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N21,814,635,087.13

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N4,842,313,122.18

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$63,768,296.18

31st Dec 2018

30th June 2018

Total (\$)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

\$59,183,665.51

\$61,495,066.44

\$63,768,296.18

3.70

7.75

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N89,953,619,684.92

N85,363,486,609.87

N70,335,662,265.00

27.89

5.38

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

NIGER STATE

Land Area: 10, 470 sq mi

Population: 5,343,260

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N27,032,795,298.64

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N9,126,750,293.89

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$52,690,776.88

\$12,500,000.00

31st Dec 2018

30th June 2018

Total (\$)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

\$61,345,344.97

\$55,747,995.99

\$65,190,776.88

16.94

6.27

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N41,792,519,380.33

N41,831,488,692.26

N40,300,423,742.82

3.70

-0.09

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

OGUN STATE

Land Area: 6,556.23 sq mi

Population: 5,024,191

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N18,491,242,908.33

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N29,583,479,438.84

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$97,154,285.23

\$5,000,000.00

31st Dec 2018

\$103,256,042.18

30th June 2018

\$105,388,666.18

Total (\$)

\$102,154,285.23

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-3.07

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-1.07

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

N95,174,172,678.30

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

N98,716,941,494.10

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

N104,933,290,271.91

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-9.30

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-3.59

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

ONDO STATE

Land Area: 6,000 sq mi

Population: 4,515,660

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N28,275,467,043.01

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N19,001,563,646.74

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$78,980,779.09

31st Dec 2018

\$79,854,005.14

30th June 2018

\$81,417,458.58

Total (\$)

\$78,980,779.09

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-2.99

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-1.09

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N55,524,221,404.56

N49,123,506,028.25

N50,610,170,334.16

9.71

13.03

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

OSUN STATE

Land Area: 3,572 sq mi

Population: 4,536,877

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N10,094,358,181.86

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N10,205,102,028.94

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$85,250,321.66

\$12,245,989.00

31st Dec 2018

\$99,085,406.37

30th June 2018

\$101,567,066.28

Total (\$)

\$97,496,310.66

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-4.01

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-1.60

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

N144,804,503,035.23

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

N148,101,237,664.94

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

N135,831,145,633.27

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

6.61

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-2.23

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

OYO STATE

Land Area: 10,986 sq mi

Population: 7,540,300

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N28,121,335,249.50

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N14,060,685,978.15

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$136,531,758.12

31st Dec 2018
\$104,997,383.47

30th June 2018
\$106,334,516.11

Total (\$)
\$136,531,758.12

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

28.40

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

30.03

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

12.90

8.57

N99,358,565,798.52

N91,515,756,366.15

N88,003,629,720.82

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

PLATEAU STATE

Land Area: 11, 936 sq mi

Population: 4,075,392

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N21,369,952,515.60

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N9,413,952,271.51

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$28,491,926.97

31st Dec 2018

\$28,874,208.63

30th June 2018

\$29,696,386.15

Total (\$)

\$28,491,926.97

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-4.06

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-1.32

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N98,356,193,262.55

N100,366,504,576.83

N121,579,460,297.29

-19.10

-2.00

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

RIVERS STATE

Land Area: 4,277 sq mi

Population: 7,023,942

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N75,843,269,695.71

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N75,974,536,695.99

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$80,915,343.53

31st Dec 2018

\$78,278,786.10

30th June 2018

\$79,520,400.99

Total (\$)

\$80,915,343.53

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

1.75

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

3.37

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

39.64

18.33

N266,936,225,793.65

N225,592,469,150.22

N191,156,694,184.66

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

SOKOTO STATE

Land Area: 10,028 sq mi

Population: 4,831,152

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N26,809,761,972.66

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N12,077,025,746.68

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$38,594,539.81

31st Dec 2018

\$39,218,901.04

30th June 2018

\$40,225,935.91

Total (\$)

\$38,594,539.81

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-4.06

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-1.59

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N33,509,692,266.79

N38,604,705,528.74

N24,891,029,854.58

34.63

-13.20

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

TARABA STATE

Land Area: 21, 032 sq mi

Population: 2,968,132

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N22,435,208,117.09

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N3,272,217,539.86

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$21,316,143.05

31st Dec 2018

30th June 2018

Total (\$)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

\$21,611,262.68

\$22,113,312.20

\$21,316,143.05

-3.60

-1.37

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N73,466,840,201.25

N61,508,573,011.13

N59,598,963,943.09

23.27

19.44

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

YOBE STATE

Land Area: 17, 568 sq mi

Population: 3,163,747

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N25,026,287,229.70

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N2,206,307,291.27

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$27,242,686.26

31st Dec 2018

\$27,486,482.07

30th June 2018

\$28,496,975.62

Total (\$)

\$27,242,686.26

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

-4.40

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

-0.89

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N27,465,573,418.77

N27,772,599,253.39

N27,317,264,912.88

0.54

-1.11

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

ZAMFARA STATE

Land Area: 15,352 sq mi

Population: 4,353,533

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N19,971,967,689.61

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N7,210,062,254.23

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$33,101,729.89

31st Dec 2018

30th June 2018

Total (\$)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

\$33,524,208.01

\$34,244,939.78

\$33,101,729.89

-3.34

-1.26

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N61,716,954,035.15

N59,900,241,661.65

N69,923,231,483.13

-11.74

3.03

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

FCT

Land Area: 15,352 sq mi

Population: 4,353,533

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N34,274,729,611.52

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N38,570,894,950.27

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$31,215,043.81

31st Dec 2018

30th June 2018

Total (\$)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

\$31,848,844.12

\$32,833,430.20

\$31,215,043.81

-4.93

-1.99

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N132,195,733,234.70

N164,245,377,802.60

N94,115,685,075.02

40.46

-19.51

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

SUB-TOTAL STATE & FCT

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N1,199,414,430,817.52

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N691,109,342,863.76

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$4,037,194,104.96

\$237,475,989.00

31st Dec 2018

\$4,230,717,052.02

30th June 2018

\$4,248,683,988.14

Total (\$)

\$4,274,670,093.96

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

0.61

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

1.04

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N3,966,219,816,141.57

N3,853,436,049,469.02

N3,477,321,000,399.57

14.06

2.93

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

FGN

Net FAAC Allocation As At H1 2019

N1,165,139,701,206.00

Total IGR As At H1 2019

N652,538,447,913.49

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$8,678,297,160.04

\$124,751,246.00

\$2,916,563,553.00

\$11,168,352,000.00

31st Dec 2018

30th June 2018

Total (\$)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

\$21,043,647,747.98

\$17,834,756,936.86

\$22,887,963,959.04

28.33

8.76

Domestic Debt Stock

DEBT STOCK (N)

DEBT STOCK DEC 2018 (N)

DEBT STOCK JUNE 2018 (N)

Y on Y GROWTH RATE (%)

Q on Q GROWTH RATE (%)

N12,774,405,701,997.00

N12,774,405,700,000.00

N12,151,437,661,592.00

5.13

0.00

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

GRAND TOTAL

External Debt Stock

Domestic Debt Stock

Notes: Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty one (31) States and FCT was as at June 30, 2019 while Domestic Debt Stock Figures for four (4) States, (Anambra Bayelsa, Benue and Nasarrawa) were as at March 31, 2019.

Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

FEDERAL GOVERNMENT DOMESTIC DEBT STOCK BY INSTRUMENT AS AT JUNE 30, 2019

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

FEDERAL GOVERNMENT DOMESTIC DEBT STOCK BY INSTRUMENT AS AT DECEMBER 31, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

FEDERAL GOVERNMENT DOMESTIC DEBT STOCK BY INSTRUMENT - HALF YEAR GROWTH RATE

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

NIGERIA'S TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT PORTFOLIO AS AT JUNE 30, 2019

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

NIGERIA'S TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT PORTFOLIO AS AT JUNE 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

NIGERIA'S TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT PORTFOLIO PERCENTAGE GROWTH RATE

Growth Rate %

A

B

C

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

Total

\$65,849.96

MULTILATERAL

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$38,311.97	\$11,428.09	\$15,972.87	-----	\$73.56	\$61.63	-----	\$487.40	\$489.25	-----

IBRD

Total

\$2,044.59

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$2,044.59	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

A.D.B

Total

\$4,426.67

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$4,235.89	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$190.78	0.00

IFAD

Total

\$91.53

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$91.53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

A.D.F

Total **\$579.76** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$281.29	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$298.46	0.00

AGTF

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

IDA

Total **\$56,278.52** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$36,222.08	\$4,563.95	\$15,843.27	0.00	\$73.56	\$61.63	0.00	\$-485.97	0.00	0.00

EDF

Total **\$1,670.54** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$1,489.12	\$181.42	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

BADEA

Total **\$29.34** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$29.41	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-\$0.07	0.00	0.00

IDB

Total **\$729.02** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$600.77	0.00	\$129.60	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-\$1.35	0.00	0.00

Total

\$8,578.17

BILATERAL

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$3,846.15	\$3,608.78	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00	\$1,123.24	0.00

EXIM BANK OF CHINA

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

NIGERIA COMMUNICATION SATELLITE

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIA NATIONAL PUBLIC SECURITY COMM. SYS. PROJECT

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIA RAILWAY MODERNISATION PROJECT (IDU KADUNA SECTION)

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIA RAILWAY MODERNISATION PROJECT (LAGOS - IBADAN SECTION)

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

NIGERIA ABUJA LIGHT RAIL PROJECT

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIA ICT INFRASTRUCTURE BACKBONE PROJECT

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIA FOUR AIRPORT TERMINALS EXPANSION PROJECT

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN ZUNGERU HYDROELECTRIC PROJECT

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

NIGERIAN REHABILITATION AND UPGRADING OF ABUJA-KEFFI-MAKURDI ROAD PROJECT

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

EXIM BANK OF INDIA

Total **\$1.50** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$1.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

FRENCH DEVELOPMENT AGENCY

Total **\$8,532.14** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$3,846.15	\$3,562.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$1,123.24	0.00

JICA

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

KFW

Total **\$44.53** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$44.53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$25.83	0.00

Total

\$157,012.17

COMMERCIAL

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$157,012.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Total

\$148574.67

EUROBONDS

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$148574.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

5.125% EUROBOND 2018

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

6.75% EUROBOND 2021

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

6.375% EUROBOND 2023

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.875% EUROBOND 2032

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.625% EUROBOND 2047

Total **\$57,187.50** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$57,187.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

6.5% EUROBOND 2027

Total **\$48,750.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$48,750.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.143% EUROBOND 2030

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.696% EUROBOND 2038

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.875% EUROBOND 2027

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

9.248% EUROBOND 2027

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

8.747% EUROBOND 2031

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.696% EUROBOND 2038

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.875% EUROBOND 2032

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

7.625% EUROBOND 2025

Total **\$42,637.17** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$42,637.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Total

\$8,437.50

Percentage of Total

0.00%

DIASPORA BOND

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$8,437.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

5.625% DIASPORA BOND 2022

Total **\$8,437.50** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$8,437.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Total

\$20,859.63

Percentage of Total

8.27%

OTHERS

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$20,859.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

AGENCY FEES

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

OIL WARRANT

Total **\$20,859.63** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$20,859.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Total

\$252,299.93

Percentage of Total

TOTAL

Principal

\$42,158.13

Interest Fee

\$192,908.67

Service Fee

\$15,972.87

Deferred Principal

0.00

Deferred Interest

\$73.56

Deferred Service Charge

\$61.63

Penalty Interest

0.00

Waiver/Credit

-\$487.40

Commitment Charges

\$1,612.49

Other Charges

0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

NATIONAL EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT JUNE 30, 2019

('million)

Sub-Total

\$12,715.49

MULTILATERAL

Percentage of Total

World Bank Group

African Development Bank Group

ADB

AGTF

\$1,243.93

IDA

IBRD

ADF

BADEA

EDF

IDB

IFAD

\$10,016.33

\$374.18

\$800.33

\$5.88

\$58.40

\$16.15

\$200.29

Sub-Total

\$3,278.80

BILATERAL

Percentage of Total

China (Exim Bank of China)

France (AFD)

Japan (JICA)

India (Exim Bank of India)

Germany (KfW)

\$2,600.14

\$362.23

\$76.72

\$27.76

\$211.95

Sub-Total

\$11,168.35

COMMERCIAL

Percentage of Total

EUROBONDS

DIASPORA BOND

\$10,868.35

\$300.00

GRAND TOTAL

\$27,162.64

Percentage of Total

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

NATIONAL EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT DECEMBER 30, 2019

('million)

Sub-Total

\$11,014.34

MULTILATERAL

Percentage of Total

World Bank Group

African Development Bank Group

ADB

\$1,264.61

AGTF

IDA

\$8,550.11

IBRD

\$124.18

ADF

\$822.73

BADEA

\$5.88

EDF

\$61.25

IDB

\$16.13

IFAD

\$169.45

Sub-Total

\$3,091.68

BILATERAL

Percentage of Total

China (Exim Bank of China)

\$2,485.08

France (AFD)

\$344.63

Japan (JICA)

\$75.16

India (Exim Bank of India)

\$14.79

Germany (KfW)

\$172.02

Sub-Total

\$11,168.35

COMMERCIAL

Percentage of Total

EUROBONDS

\$10,868.35

DIASPORA BOND

\$300.00

GRAND TOTAL

\$25,274.36

Percentage of Total

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2019

NATIONAL EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK QUARTER ON QUARTER GROWTH PERCENTAGE

('million)

MULTILATERAL

World Bank Group

IDA	IBRD
17.15%	201.32%

African Development Bank Group

ADF	BADEA	EDF	IDB	IFAD
-2.72%	-0.03%	-4.66%	0.10%	18.20%

ADB	AGTF
-1.64%	-----

BILATERAL

China (Exim Bank of China)
4.63%

France (AFD)
5.11%

Japan (JICA)
2.07%

India (Exim Bank of India)
87.67%

Germany (KfW)
23.22%

COMMERCIAL

EUROBONDS
0.00%

DIASPORA BOND
0.00%

GRAND TOTAL

Methodology

Data is supplied administratively by the Debt Management Office, Nigeria and verified and validated by the National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria.

NIGERIA'S TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT PORTFOLIO AS AT JUNE 30, 2019

Public Debt Stock - External and Domestic Debt of the FGN, States and FCT as at June 30, 2019

	Debt Category	Amount Outstanding (US\$'M)	Amount Outstanding (N'M)	% of Total
A.	Total External Debt	27,162.63	8,322,629.83	32.38%
	FGN Only	22,887.96	7,012,870.94	27.29%
	States & FCT	4,274.67	1,309,758.89	5.10%
B.	Total Domestic Debt	56,720.03	17,379,015.91	67.62%
	FGN Only	43,775.44	13,412,796.09	52.19%
	States & FCT	12,944.58	3,966,219.82	15.43%
C.	Total Public Debt(A+B)	83,882.66	25,701,645.74	100%

Public Debt Stock - External and Domestic Debt of the FGN, States and FCT as at June 30, 2018

Debt Category	Amount Outstanding (US\$'M) June 2018	Amount Outstanding (N'M) June 2018	% of Total
Total External Debt	22,083.44	6,750,907.61	30.17
FGN only	17,834.76	5,475,270.38	24.47
States & FCT	4,248.68	1,304,345.98	5.83
Total Domestic Debt	51,124.50	15,695,221.50	70.13
FGN Only	39,749.55	12,151,437.66	54.30
States & FCT	11,374.95	3,477,321.00	15.54
Total Public Debt(A+B)	73,207.94	22,379,666.27	100.00

Debt Category	Growth rate % (Amount Outstanding (US\$'M) June 2018)	Growth rate % (Amount Outstanding (N'M) June 2018)
Total External Debt	23.00	23.28
FGN only	28.33	28.08
States & FCT	0.61	0.41
Total Domestic Debt	10.94	10.73
FGN Only	10.13	10.38
States & FCT	13.80	14.06
Total Public Debt(A+B)	14.58	14.84

Nigeria's External Debt Stock as at June 30, 2019			Nigeria's External Debt Stock as at December 30, 2019			
in Millions of USD			in Millions of USD			
Category	Outstanding Debt	Percentage of Total	Category	Outstanding Debt	Percentage of Total	Quarter on Quarter Growth %
MULTILATERAL			MULTILATERAL			
World Bank Group			World Bank Group			
IDA	10,016.33		IDA	8,550.11		17.15
IBRD	374.18		IBRD	124.18		201.32
African Development Bank Group			African Development Bank Group			
ADB	1,243.93		ADB	1,264.61		-1.64
AGTF	-		AGTF	-		
ADF	800.33		ADF	822.73		-2.72
BADEA	5.88		BADEA	5.88		-0.03
EDF	58.40		EDF	61.25		-4.66
IDB	16.15		IDB	16.13		0.10
IFAD	200.29		IFAD	169.45		18.20
SUB-TOTAL	12,715.49	46.81%	SUB-TOTAL	11,014.34	43.58%	15.44
BILATERAL			BILATERAL			
China (Exim Bank of China)	2,600.14		China (Exim Bank of China)	2,485.08		4.63
France (AFD)	362.23		France (AFD)	344.63		5.11
Japan (JICA)	76.72		Japan (JICA)	75.16		2.07
India (Exim Bank of India)	27.76		India (Exim Bank of India)	14.79		87.67
Germany (KFW)	211.95		Germany (KFW)	172.02		23.22
SUB-TOTAL	3,278.80	12.07%	SUB-TOTAL	3,091.68	12.23%	6.05
COMMERCIAL			COMMERCIAL			
EUROBONDS	10,868.35		EUROBONDS	10,868.35		0.00
DIASPORA BOND	300.00		DIASPORA BOND	300.00		0.00
SUB-TOTAL	11,168.35	41.12%	SUB-TOTAL	11,168.35	44.19%	0.00
GRAND TOTAL	27,162.64	100.00%	GRAND TOTAL	25,274.36	100.00%	7.47

Federal Government, States and FCT's External Debt Stock as at 30th June, 2019

S/No	States and FGN	Multilateral	Bilateral (AFD)	Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)	Commercial(EuroBo nds & diaspora Bond)	Total
		(\$)	(\$)	(\$)		(\$)
1	Abia	98,028,293.33	-	-	-	98,028,293.33
2	Adamawa	94,113,674.40	6,500,000.00	-	-	100,613,674.40
3	Akwa Ibom	44,935,625.88	-	-	-	44,935,625.88
4	Anambra	111,783,998.80	-	-	-	111,783,998.80
5	Bauchi	133,705,364.22	-	-	-	133,705,364.22
6	Bayelsa	56,154,690.84	-	-	-	56,154,690.84
7	Benue	33,936,861.92	-	-	-	33,936,861.92
8	Borno	21,313,198.49	-	-	-	21,313,198.49
9	Cross River	148,830,721.41	43,900,000.00	-	-	192,730,721.41
10	Delta	62,952,056.49	-	-	-	62,952,056.49
11	Ebonyi	76,044,993.97	-	-	-	76,044,993.97
12	Edo	277,735,972.77	-	-	-	277,735,972.77
13	Ekiti	104,771,792.18	-	-	-	104,771,792.18
14	Enugu	118,851,839.26	6,500,000.00	-	-	125,351,839.26
15	Gombe	36,960,036.41	-	-	-	36,960,036.41
16	Imo	61,812,739.83	7,000,000.00	-	-	68,812,739.83
17	Jigawa	31,550,317.67	-	-	-	31,550,317.67
18	Kaduna	223,760,252.12	-	-	-	223,760,252.12
19	Kano	62,219,720.77	-	-	-	62,219,720.77
20	Katsina	61,082,288.27	-	-	-	61,082,288.27
21	Kebbi	44,918,042.07	-	-	-	44,918,042.07
22	Kogi	31,111,476.95	-	-	-	31,111,476.95
23	Kwara	47,961,939.95	-	-	-	47,961,939.95
24	Lagos	1,277,404,576.50	143,830,000.00	-	-	1,421,234,576.50
25	Nassarawa	63,768,296.18	-	-	-	63,768,296.18
26	Niger	52,690,776.88	12,500,000.00	-	-	65,190,776.88
27	Ogun	97,154,285.23	5,000,000.00	-	-	102,154,285.23
28	Ondo	78,980,779.09	-	-	-	78,980,779.09
29	Osun	85,250,321.66	12,245,989.00	-	-	97,496,310.66
30	Oyo	136,531,758.12	-	-	-	136,531,758.12
31	Plateau	28,491,926.97	-	-	-	28,491,926.97
32	Rivers	80,915,343.53	-	-	-	80,915,343.53
33	Sokoto	38,594,539.81	-	-	-	38,594,539.81
34	Taraba	21,316,143.05	-	-	-	21,316,143.05
35	Yobe	27,242,686.26	-	-	-	27,242,686.26
36	Zamfara	33,101,729.89	-	-	-	33,101,729.89
37	FCT	31,215,043.81	-	-	-	31,215,043.81
Sub-Total State & FCT		4,037,194,104.96	237,475,989.00	-	-	4,274,670,093.96
FGN		8,678,297,160.04	124,751,246.00	2,916,563,553.00	11,168,352,000.00	22,887,963,959.04
Grand Total		12,715,491,265.00	362,227,235.00	2,916,563,553.00	11,168,352,000.00	27,162,634,053.00
	Arrears owed by States	12,715,491,265.00				
	Total States without Arrears					
						27,162,634,053.00
						-
Percentage of States' DebtStock to the Total Debt Stock						16%
Percentage of Federal Government's DebtStock to the Total Debt Stock						84%
						100%

Federal Government, States and FCT's External Debt Stock as at 31 December 2018							Federal Government		
S/No	States and FGN	Multilateral (\$)	Bilateral (AFD) (\$)	Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$)	Commercial(EuroBonds & diaspora Bond)	Total (\$)	States and FCT's External Debt		
							Stock as at at	Year on Year Growth %	Quarter on Quarter
							30 June 2018	Growth %	Growth %
1	Abia	98,582,798.91	-	-	-	98,582,798.91	100,217,589.59	-2.18	-0.56
2	Adamawa	91,290,423.73	6,500,000.00	-	-	97,790,423.73	57,860,541.54	73.89	2.89
3	Akwa Ibom	45,657,647.14	-	-	-	45,657,647.14	48,385,866.53	-7.13	-1.58
4	Anambra	107,041,487.48	-	-	-	107,041,487.48	107,438,517.03	4.04	4.43
5	Bauchi	133,930,757.08	-	-	-	133,930,757.08	134,907,612.92	-0.89	-0.17
6	Bayelsa	56,623,178.71	-	-	-	56,623,178.71	57,256,211.04	-1.92	-0.83
7	Benue	39,610,851.64	-	-	-	39,610,851.64	34,750,363.40	-2.34	-14.32
8	Borno	21,618,240.11	-	-	-	21,618,240.11	22,292,486.47	-4.39	-1.41
9	Cross River	144,873,736.81	43,900,000.00	-	-	188,773,736.81	193,796,061.81	-0.55	2.10
10	Delta	63,286,948.43	-	-	-	63,286,948.43	63,825,838.81	-1.37	-0.53
11	Ebonyi	66,653,026.12	-	-	-	66,653,026.12	67,901,721.07	11.99	14.09
12	Edo	276,253,922.96	-	-	-	276,253,922.96	279,029,896.21	-0.46	0.54
13	Ekiti	106,208,598.19	-	-	-	106,208,598.19	97,994,770.66	6.92	-1.35
14	Enugu	119,677,662.23	6,500,000.00	-	-	126,177,662.23	127,952,029.92	-2.03	-0.65
15	Gombe	37,406,069.57	-	-	-	37,406,069.57	38,500,292.18	-4.00	-1.19
16	Imo	59,515,586.62	-	-	-	59,515,586.62	61,277,993.68	12.30	15.62
17	Jigawa	32,008,444.77	-	-	-	32,008,444.77	32,800,038.17	-3.81	-1.43
18	Kaduna	227,252,685.58	-	-	-	227,252,685.58	232,965,533.73	-3.95	-1.54
19	Kano	63,409,069.74	-	-	-	63,409,069.74	65,047,427.46	-4.35	-1.88
20	Katsina	62,133,706.90	-	-	-	62,133,706.90	64,757,964.40	-5.68	-1.69
21	Kebbi	45,605,534.73	-	-	-	45,605,534.73	46,759,780.42	-3.94	-1.51
22	Kogi	31,584,158.36	-	-	-	31,584,158.36	32,371,905.62	-3.89	-1.50
23	Kwara	48,599,040.43	-	-	-	48,599,040.43	49,871,457.19	-3.83	-1.31
24	Lagos	1,282,598,935.47	143,830,000.00	-	-	1,426,428,935.47	1,451,639,937.86	-2.09	-0.36
25	Nassarawa	59,183,665.51	-	-	-	59,183,665.51	61,495,066.44	3.70	7.75
26	Niger	54,845,344.97	6,500,000.00	-	-	61,345,344.97	55,747,995.99	16.94	6.27
27	Ogun	98,256,042.18	5,000,000.00	-	-	103,256,042.18	105,388,666.18	-3.07	-1.07
28	Ondo	79,854,005.14	-	-	-	79,854,005.14	81,417,458.58	-2.99	-1.09
29	Osun	86,839,417.37	12,245,989.00	-	-	99,085,406.37	101,567,066.28	-4.01	-1.60
30	Oyo	104,997,383.47	-	-	-	104,997,383.47	106,334,516.11	28.40	30.03
31	Plateau	28,874,208.63	-	-	-	28,874,208.63	29,696,386.15	-4.06	-1.32
32	Rivers	78,278,786.10	-	-	-	78,278,786.10	79,520,400.99	1.75	3.37
33	Sokoto	39,218,901.04	-	-	-	39,218,901.04	40,225,935.91	-4.06	-1.59
34	Taraba	21,611,262.68	-	-	-	21,611,262.68	22,113,312.20	-3.60	-1.37
35	Yobe	27,486,482.07	-	-	-	27,486,482.07	28,496,975.62	-4.40	-0.89
36	Zamfara	33,524,208.01	-	-	-	33,524,208.01	34,244,939.78	-3.34	-1.26
37	FCT	31,848,844.12	-	-	-	31,848,844.12	32,833,430.20	-4.93	-1.99
Sub-Total State & FCT		4,006,241,063.02	224,475,989.00	-	-	4,230,717,052.02	4,248,683,988.14	0.61	1.04
FGN		7,008,095,136.98	120,153,811.00	2,747,046,800.00	11,168,352,000.00	21,043,647,747.98	17,834,756,936.86	28.33	8.76
Grand Total		11,014,336,200.00	344,629,800.00	2,747,046,800.00	11,168,352,000.00	25,274,364,800.00	22,083,440,925.00	23.00	7.47

FEDERAL GOVERNMENT DOMESTIC DEBT STOCK BY INSTRUMENT AS AT JUNE 30, 2019

INSTRUMENT	AMOUNTS IN NAIRA	% PROPORTION
FGN Bonds	9,691,417.04	72.26
Nigerian Treasury Bills	2,651,514.04	19.77
Nigerian Treasury Bonds	125,988.00	0.94
FGN Savings Bond	10,431.84	0.08
FGN Sukuk	200,000.00	1.49
Green Bond	25,690.00	0.19
Promissory Notes	707,755.17	5.28
TOTAL	13,412,796.09	100.00

Federal Government Domestic Debt Stock by Instrument as at December 31, 2018

Instruments	Amounts in Naira	% of Total	Growth Rate %
FGN Bonds	9,334,737.98	73.07%	3.82
Nigerian Treasury Bills	2,735,967.54	21.42%	- 3.09
Nigerian Treasury Bonds	150,988.00	1.18%	- 16.56
FGN Savings Bond	10,750.44	0.08%	- 2.96
FGN Sukuk	200,000.00	1.57%	-
Green Bond	10,690.00	0.08%	140.32
Promissory Notes	331,271.74	2.59%	113.65
TOTAL	12,774,405.70	100.00%	5.00

Nigeria's Actual External Debt Service Payments in Second Quarter, 2019
in Thousands of USD

Category	Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/ Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges	Total	Percentage of Total
MULTILATERAL	38,311.97	11,428.09	15,972.87	-	73.56	61.63	-	487.40	489.25	-	65,849.96	26.10%
IBRD	0.00	2,044.59	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2,044.59	
A.D.B	0.00	4,235.89	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	190.78	0.00	4,426.67	
IFAD	0.00	91.53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	91.53	
A.D.F	0.00	281.29	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	298.46	0.00	579.76	
AGTF	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
IDA	36,222.08	4,563.95	15,843.27	0.00	73.56	61.63	0.00	-485.97	0.00	0.00	56,278.52	
EDF	1,489.12	181.42	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,670.54	
BADEA	0.00	29.41	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.07	0.00	0.00	29.34	
IDB	600.77	0.00	129.60	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1.35	0.00	0.00	729.02	
BILATERAL	3,846.15	3,608.78	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,123.24	0.00	8,578.17	3.40%
EXIM Bank of China	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria Communication Sattelite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria National Public Security Comm. Sys. Project	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria Railway Modernisation Project (Idu Kaduna Section)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria Railway Modernisation Project (Lagos - Ibadan Section)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria Abuja Light Rail Project	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria ICT Infrastructure Backbone Project	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria Four Airport Terminals Expansion Project	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigerian Zungeru Hydroelectric Project	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigerian Rehabilitation and Upgrading of Abuja-Keffi-Makurdi Road Project	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
EXIM Bank of India	0.00	1.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.50	
French Development Agency	3,846.15	3,562.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,123.24	0.00	8,532.14	
JICA	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
KFW	0.00	44.53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	44.53	
COMMERCIAL	0.00	157,012.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	157,012.17	62.23%
EUROBONDS	0.00	148,574.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	148,574.67	
5.125% Eurobond 2018	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
6.75% Eurobond 2021	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
6.375% Eurobond 2023	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
7.875% Eurobond 2032	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
7.625% Eurobond 2047	0.00	57,187.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	57,187.50	
6.5% Eurobond 2027	0.00	48,750.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	48,750.00	
7.143% Eurobond 2030	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
7.696% Eurobond 2038	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
7.875% Eurobond 2027	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
9.248% Eurobond 2027	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
8.747% Eurobond 2031	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
7.696% Eurobond 2038	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
7.875% Eurobond 2032	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
7.625% Eurobond 2025	0.00	42,637.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	42,637.17	
DIASPORA BOND	0.00	8,437.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	8,437.50	
5.625% Diaspora Bond 2022	0.00	8,437.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	8,437.50	
OTHERS	0.00	20,859.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20,859.63	8.27%
Agency Fees	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
OIL WARRANT	0.00	20,859.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20,859.63	
TOTAL	42,158.13	192,908.67	15,972.87	0.00	73.56	61.63	0.00	-	487.40	1,612.49	252,299.93	100%

Federal Government Actual Domestic Debt Service for April - June, 2019

(Amount in Naira)

Instruments	April	May	June	Total
NTBs				
Interest	14,897,947,747.19	14,700,317,313.85	16,113,483,121.45	45,711,748,182.49
Federal Govt. Bonds				
Interest	69,184,981,715.55	31,779,137,060.69	28,027,002,739.73	128,991,121,515.97
Treasury Bonds				
Interest	-	3125000000	3125000000	6,250,000,000.00
Principal	-	-	-	
FGNSB				
Interest	112,381,123.27	100,208,236.88	98,031,264.55	310,620,624.70
FGN SUKUK	-	-	-	
Interest			7849934247	7,849,934,246.58
FGN Green Bond	-	-	-	
Interest	-	-	718532011	718,532,010.96
TOTAL INTEREST	84,195,310,586.01	49,704,662,611.42	55,931,983,383.27	189,831,956,580.70

Acknowledgements/Contacts

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